

IMPACT OF VIRTUAL REALITY ON LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AND THE DAMAGE CAUSED TO THE MODERN WORLD

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Abstract: One of the things in the world today that is expanding the quickest is technology. All people's lives, from adults to children, have benefited greatly from such technology, yet it has also brought about numerous negative effects. Particularly, students' lives have been completely transformed by technology. We can then determine the benefits and drawbacks of technology and its overall influence on society. In the modern world, technology has an impact on many facets of life, including food, healthcare, security, and transportation. Particularly, those engaged in online cyberattacks have tried to get personal data and exploit it to demand ransom payments from victims. Students have benefited immensely from artificial intelligence (AI) in education and several other technological domains. The internet is useful. Compared to reading books, pupils can learn more efficiently online. Aside from that, it has helped the commercial, industrial, and communication sectors. We utilize technology in our daily lives to move from place to place, make meals, and clean clothes.

Keywords: learning environment, impact of ICT, information era

1. Introduction

Over the past 10 years, several universities with the common goal of promoting educational innovation have invested in centers for educational innovation that give priority to emerging technology. Among the most popular new educational technologies include virtual reality, blockchain, internet of things, and artificial intelligence. In particular, there are several reasons why virtual reality has to catch on quickly at this time. Virtual reality offers a number of advantages that make it a popular option for use in teaching and learning in higher education. Moreover, costs have generally dropped, making integration into the classroom more practical [1-3].

A recent global survey found that traditional lectures are more prevalent and have a greater impact in STEM courses than active learning. With an immersive virtual reality experience that allows them to engage hands-on with the material, students may enjoy a unique active-learning experience suitable for a variety of STEM courses [4-7].

These chances were mostly made possible by the desire of students to "live" science. That experience is often limited since certain chemical events occur at the molecular level. Because they only see the final result of reagent manipulation rather than the processes and chemical interactions that lead to it, students are thus given a false perception of reality. Because of this, one advantage of these apps is that they provide an environment in which students may interact with a subject from several perspectives and get knowledge from viewpoints that are difficult to find in other contexts [8,9].

Therefore, this article discusses about the impact of virtual learning environment on the final outcome of the students.

2. Technology's Harmful Effects on Society:

2.1 Social Disconnect

Because of the internet, people are now physically closer to one another, yet emotionally, distance has increased in many situations. Individuals are always preoccupied with occupying their virtual worlds. They become into formality and lose sight of friends and family, who make up the actual world[10]. Although technology advances industry and the education of pupils, it also enslaves individuals to it. Depression and other mental health issues result from this. According to the study, using technology reduced pleasure and general life satisfaction. Lack of sleep, obesity, inattention poor the classroom, a decline in closeness and communication between friends and family, and unwelcome involvements like cyberbullying have all resulted from this [11,12].

Reduced in-person interaction: People are more introverted and alone these days since they prefer online communication over in-person contact. Another disadvantage is that we cannot express our true feelings or what we want to convey through email or social networking sites. So, in order to properly express our feelings to them, we had to have face-to-face conversations [13, 14]. Children who use ICT gadgets are also spending more time online and developing false beliefs that contribute to a rise in extramarital affairs and cybercrimes.

2.2 Decreased Exercise/Health Issues

Users who use ICT gadgets may become more sedentary. Constant use of this might lead to many health problems, such as headaches, neck discomfort, physical and mental stress, obesity, diabetes, heart disease, and eyestrain from repetitive strain injuries. Children get bored by watching cartoons, playing video games online, and feeling uncomfortable among other children. These activities might deter children from going outside. Due to its lack of physical exercise, this lifestyle increases our risk of health issues [15,16].

2.3 Price

Many ICT gadgets are expensive. As such, their purchase and maintenance are reasonably priced. The educational institutions prevent less fortunate students from taking use of e-learning. Employment loss: Employment losses may arise from the automation of physical work [17, 18]. The significance of technology and the advantages of ICT People from all walks of life may now obtain a variety of necessities thanks to technology. Additionally, technology is utilized to provide possibilities that would not otherwise be available to those in need of a particular kind of help and to enhance the quality of life for such individuals. Numerous technologies like computers and cellphones have evolved as a result of modern technology [19].

We may keep and manage the data pertaining to our everyday schedules using ICT gadgets. We may also group the devices in our house for common use and management. We may also utilize online trading, internet payments, and net banking to purchase daily requirements. We'll save time by not having to spend it shopping and making purchases. Social Bond: We can connect and establish relationships with people worldwide in our daily lives because to ICT. By utilizing the Internet and communication channels, people may communicate via email, social networking websites, mobile phones, and other methods. It saves time and runs inexpensively. Bulletin boards and discussion groups are available [20]. Bulletin boards and discussion groups are examples of services that let you interact with lots of people at once.

2.4 Information Exchange

Nowadays, information is readily available to us. We have access to any information at any time, anywhere. Through email and online discussion forums such as Google Groups and Yahoo! Groups, people may share information, news, ideas, and more with one other beyond geographical

boundaries. Global understanding of cultures, beliefs, ideas, and lifestyles is facilitated via information sharing. They increase mutual regard and promote openness [21, 22].

2.5 Interaction

We are able to communicate with each other without any difficulties. It becomes quicker since we can send a message right away for a nominal cost in a short length of time, saving money and labor for the delivery. For that, you can use teleconferencing, video conferencing, and email. Using the video conferencing strategy, which simulates face-to-face communication, may help us meet or communicate with each other more successfully [23, 24].

2.6 Use of Free Time

It is possible to entertain yourself using ICT. We have access to a variety of media in addition to viewing or listening to the news, including games, movies, music, gaming, and much more [25, 26]. Children's Education: ICT creates new learning opportunities through e-learning, virtual learning, online resources, remote learning, and interactive multimedia. Participation in these diverse learning and teaching activities is open to students worldwide. We might use virtual to do the unfeasible experiments [27].

These many educational and instructional programs are open to students worldwide. For the impracticable trials, virtual reality and simulations can be used. A virtual classroom for online learning is created when instructors and students log in at the same time and pace. For the sake of our children's future, this is a prudent investment.

2.7 Independent Contractor

Technology tools for information and communication make our jobs easier. It will not be a problem for us to start our own companies, purchase goods and sell them in the market, or run advertising campaigns using multimedia apps. The positive and negative effects of ICT on our daily lives are selling well, which helps small businesses. Online or net banking payment options are available to us [28].

2.8 Environment Without Papers

ICT uses its gadgets, not paper, to store and retrieve information. By reducing the demand for paper, ICT use helps to save forests and enhances environmental quality [29].

2.9 Increasing Knowledge about Health

When we obtain timely input from doctors, we recover faster. Health literacy is the need that individuals use and acquire high-quality information about diseases and drugs via online health care services that are available through ICT devices [30–32].

3 Conclusion

It can be concluded that even though the information technology plays a major roles in the education and also the other related fields, there are some disadvantages too. It should be promptly monitored to go for an efficient use of information technology in the modern era to reduce and eradicate the problem to the young generations.

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